

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Effect of soil amendments on rice and wheat yields in salt-affected soils

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More than 0.17 million ha in the Indira Gandhi Canal Command is affected by moderate to severe salinity and sodicity. We studied the effect of organic manure and gypsum on rice and wheat yields in Typic Salorthid, fine-textured, salt-affected soils in a split-plot design (Table 1). Farmyard manure (FYM) was the main plot treatment (0, 5, 10, 20, and 40 t/ha) and gypsum was the subplot treatment (0, 5, 10, 15, and 20 t/ha).

Rice variety Jhona 349 was transplanted in the wet season and wheat variety C591 was sown as the dry season crop. N at 100 kg/ha and P at 18 kg/ha were applied after adjusting for N supplied by FYM.

FYM significantly increased rice and wheat yields (Table 2).

Gypsum did not significantly affect yields. □

Table 1. Characteristics of experimental soil profile, Typic Salorthid, Bikaner (Raj.), India.

Depth (cm)	pH	ECe (mmho/cm)	ESP ^a	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	CaCO ₃ (%)
0-18	8.7	6.0	39.6	36.7	25.5	11.2
18-72	9.2	7.5	62.5	45.1	43.8	11.6
72-99	9.5	10.4	58.5	34.4	15.8	11.0
99-140	9.0	22.7	56.4	50.4	28.4	12.6
140-172	9.0	26.3	66.0	27.9	23.0	9.4

^aExchangeable sodium percentage.

Table 2. Yield of rice and wheat with farmyard manure and gypsum application. Bikaner, India.

FYM (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha) with indicated amount of gypsum					Mean yield (t/ha)
	0 gypsum	5 t/ha	10 t/ha	15 t/ha	20 t/ha	
	<i>Rice^a</i>					
0	1.3	1.4	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.6
5	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.9	1.8	1.7
10	2.0	1.8	2.1	1.7	1.8	1.9
20	2.2	1.5	2.4	2.1	2.1	2.1
40	2.3	2.5	2.7	2.3	1.8	2.3
Mean	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.9
	<i>Wheat^b</i>					
0	1.1	1.0	1.3	1.2	1.8	1.3
5	1.0	1.3	1.5	1.2	1.8	1.4
10	1.9	1.5	1.4	1.7	1.2	1.5
20	1.3	1.6	1.9	1.6	1.5	1.6
40	2.2	2.1	1.6	2.1	1.8	2.0
Mean	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6

^aCD = 5.57 with FYM, ns with gypsum. ^bCD = 2.68 with FYM and ns with gypsum.

Rice - fish cultivation in the hilly region of Karnataka, India

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We evaluated rearing of different species of fish to the fingerling stage in ricefields. A trench 1.5 m wide and 0.9 m deep was dug in the center of each of three 360-m² plots. Corrugations 0.3 m wide and 0.15 m deep were made on either side every 6 m to help the fish to move along the trench. Plot bunds were raised to 45 cm high. The trenches covered 14% of the total plot area.

Fertilizer was applied at transplanting of 30-d-old Intan rice seedlings. Topdressing with 50% recommended N

Fish harvest in a rice - fish system for the hilly region of Karnataka, India.

Fish	Length			Weight			Survival (%)
	Initial (mm)	At harvest (mm)	Times increase over initial	Initial (g)	At harvest (g)	Times increase over initial	
Catla	23	51	2.22	1.81	12.31	6.8	69.3
Rohu	24	54	2.25	1.93	9.48	4.9	48.1
Mrigal	22	57	2.59	1.87	10.68	5.7	65.7
Common carp	26	61	2.35	1.95	25.49	13.1	71.4
Mean	24	56	2.35	1.90	14.49	7.6	63.6

was done 30 d after transplanting (DT). Carbofuran granules were applied at transplanting to protect the crop against pests. For plankton production, plots were manured with cow dung before fish were stocked. Fish at the fry stage were released in the ratio of 4 catla:2 rohu: 1 mrigal:and 3 common carp 20 DT at

50,000/ha (each plot received 1.800 fish fry). The plot was manured once a month and the fish fed regularly. After 100 d in the field, fingerlings were harvested and survival, length, and weight of each species recorded. Rice was harvested 6 d after fish.

Average fish survival was 63.6%; it

was highest with common carp (71.4%), and lowest with rohu (48.1%) (see table). Weight increase of common carp was 13.07 times initial weight. Weights of other species increased 4.91-6.80 times. Although the rice area was reduced

14%, there was little difference in grain yield from plots with fish (4.6 t/ha) and control plots (4.7 t/ha). The additional cost incurred in raising fingerlings (preparation of trench, fish stock, feed, labor) was \$485/ha per 100 d. (Only

10% of the cost of trench preparation is taken to calculate cost of one season). The total return from fish yield was \$751/ha per 100 d. Net return was \$266/ha per 100 d. □

Rice-based crop rotations for upland fields

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Upland crop rotations were tried 1980-81 under partially irrigated conditions at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, Koraput (884 m, 18°20' N, 82°30' E) in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Short-duration rice was direct sown during the wet season under rainfed conditions, followed by wheat cultivar Utkalika, gardenpea Bonneville, chickpea JG62, mustard M-27, and potato Kufri Chandramukhi in the dry season (DS). Rice varieties used were OR 165-24-12 in 1980 and Culture-I in 1981, both with 90 d duration.

The rice received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha in 1980 and 40-9-17 kg in 1981. DS crops received the recommended package of practices. The soil was red clay loam with 5.1 pH, EC 0.168 dS/m, 0.68% organic C, 0.06% total N, 5 kg available P, and 320 kg available K/ha.

Highest yield (20.9 t/ha) was with rice - potato (see table). Rice - potato also was most efficient. Single crop rice was the most inefficient. Highest net profit was with rice - potato (see figure). □

Efficiency of crop rotations under partially irrigated conditions. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Crop rotation	Yield (t/ha)		Protein ^a (t/ha)	Carbohydrate ^a (t/ha)	Energy ^a (MJ × 10 ³ /ha)
	Wet season	Dry season			
Rice - fallow	1.9	—	0.1	1.0	18.2
Rice - wheat	1.7	3.0	0.4	3.0	59.0
Rice - gardenpea (green pod)	1.7	2.5	0.2	1.1	21.4
Rice - chickpea	1.7	0.7	0.2	1.3	26.8
Rice - mustard	1.7	0.8	0.1	1.1	34.4
Rice - potato	2.0	18.9	0.4	4.7	84.3

^aProtein, carbohydrate, and energy components were calculated for edible portions only, per standards fixed by the National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR), Hyderabad, India.

Efficiency of crop rotations in terms of net profit. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Zinc required for a rice - wheat sequence in alkali soils

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We evaluated Zn levels needed for a rice - wheat crop rotation in field experiments in the alkali soils of

Kumarganj. Experimental fields had pH 10.2-10.4, ESP 70-90 and EC 2-2.5 mmho/cm in 1:2 soil-water suspension. Gypsum (14% S) at 12 t or pyrite (30% S) at 4.5 t/ha had been added to improve soil conditions before the first rice crop in 1976. Plot size was 6 × 3.5 m in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Short-duration semidwarf Pusa 2-21 was transplanted at 15 × 15 cm with 4-

Table 1. Zn requirement of transplanted rite Pusa 2-21 in alkali soils of Kumarganj, India.

Zn (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) at foliar spray intervals of		
	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk
0	0.6	0.5	0.9
3.4	1.71.5		1.1
6.8	2.52.2		1.7
10.0	2.1	3.4	2.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3		